

POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF YOUTH IN THE MASS MEDIA

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Abstract. *In modern society, the role of mass media in political processes, social behavior and reforms is increasing. Taking this into account, this article paid particular attention to the issue of political activity of young people in mass media.*

Keywords: *mass media, political activism, youth, citizens, political life, democratization, modern society.*

In the process of democratization, today's Uzbekistan pays serious attention to the issue of citizen participation in political life, adoption and implementation of political decisions, as well as indirect or direct control over government activities. For this reason, he believes it is very important to increase the level of youth participation in political processes. Because their participation in politics is an important indicator of how much this sphere of life contributes to the realization of not only the interests of large social groups, but also the requests of various mass youth movements.

“We can recognize and emphasize that the new Uzbekistan will be built by young people with modern knowledge and a new worldview, who think creatively.” It should be noted that in the context of changes in social institutions, the worldview and political consciousness of the younger generation is influenced by various political forces, which, including the media, take advantage of the inconsistency and instability of the political views of the younger generation. People. Their main goal is also to build their political capital and gain a competitive advantage.

The media are the undisputed leader in shaping the worldview and political culture of the younger generation, providing a targeted impact on political consciousness and behavior. Despite the fact that young people are always ready to participate in political life, including in various social movements, using in some cases the resources of the media, they find a way to fully realize their personal interests, but do not always take into account their aspirations. On the one hand, this is reflected in their growing sense of dissatisfaction, and on the other hand, in the methods of carrying out their socio-political activities, expressed in their reluctance to participate in politics, in particular, in projects related to this field. Because some young people do not see their place and purpose in these processes. Consequently, the problem of studying the mechanisms of inclusion of young people in the system of political relations and relations, ways and means of eliminating their apoliticality is becoming particularly relevant.

Therefore, it becomes relevant to increase the level of political activity of young people in the media, which are becoming an integral part of modern society. Naturally, state institutions and civil society institutions are assigned special responsibilities and tasks.

First of all, an important task of the state and civil society institutions is to create the necessary conditions for the active participation of young people in the formation and development of democracy in the country, to protect the interests of the group, as well as to implement a life strategy and achieve personal success. One of these institutions is the media, which helps to

critically comprehend the activities of political subjects, determine their interests and realize the need to protect the political values of their social group.

The media, which receive special attention as one of the important conditions for the democratization of society and ensuring the political freedom of young people, include newspapers, magazines, newsletters, news agencies, television (cable, terrestrial cable television) and radio. radio broadcasts, documentary films, electronic information systems, it is also well known that state, independent and other public periodicals with permanent titles are mass media. It is no secret that the media play a huge role and importance in the implementation of democratic reforms and the formation of a new worldview in the minds of young people. So, since the media are the only instrument that regulates and connects social relations between political authorities and citizens, and also ensures transparency between them, the issue of increasing the participation of young people in them is acute. To implement this issue, which is considered serious, large-scale work is being carried out in the country in the field of public policy regarding youth. The head of our state is taking the system of supporting youth policy in Uzbekistan to a completely new level. Over the past time, a special system has been created to fully support young people, protect their rights and legitimate interests, and educate young people capable of taking responsibility for the future of the country. The beneficial aspects of this system and its effectiveness can be seen in the increased activity of youth in the political arena. In particular, this is exemplified by the daily participation of young people in the media and the growing number of political events. Here it would be useful to clarify the concept of political activity.

From the point of view of political psychology, the political activity of young people makes it possible to increase a person's self-esteem by satisfying his deepest needs. This is determined by the political disappearance of internal psychological tension. According to O. M. Karpenko and I. A. Lomanov, five components that make up the content of political activity can be distinguished: intellectual, pre-election, social, structural and professional types of political activity. So, based on these data, the phrase "political activity of young people in the media" can be understood as the level of activity in the process of covering socio-political reforms in the media.

The world is already very different from what it was in past centuries. In modern society we have the Internet and most people use social media every day. For young people, a social network is not only a place to communicate with friends, but also one of the tools for influencing politics.

It is known that the media is a general concept. Above, the media include a set of periodicals, radio, television, video programs and other forms. So, socio-political processes, in particular, announcements in the media, ensure the rapid delivery of information to participants in modern civil society, especially young People.

Young people are an active part of the country's population, which requires them to study changing social conditions, including analysis of their political activity. In general, the existential need to strengthen, renew and modernize any society and its political sphere in particular cannot be satisfied without the active participation of the younger generation in political processes.

The problems of the formation and development of youth political activity have been studied by philosophers, sociologists, political scientists and psychologists in all periods of social thought. If we talk about Uzbekistan, then in different periods of its existence, different ideas about an active person were formed in society, the content of the concept of political activity was analyzed, and the factors and motives guiding human activity were studied. Many sociological

studies note that the popularity of traditional media sources such as television, radio and print is growing every day, especially among young people. Among this category of citizens, sociologists note the unsystematic and often false information from the latest sources of mass information and communication - the Internet, social networks and instant messengers. Such sources, with sufficient control on the part of government institutions and bodies, serve to stabilize the political activity and political sentiments of young people in modern conditions.

At the 19th World Sociological Congress held in 2018, a number of speakers highlighted the emergence of such phenomena as digital humanity, the use of networks, as well as the cultural degradation of the entire human civilization as negative consequences of the spread of digitalization of society. It's no secret that similar events occur in modern society. It is the participation of young people in such processes under the control of relevant organizations that helps prevent a number of crimes.

Modern society is experiencing global changes due to the development of the latest information and communication systems and technologies. These changes, associated with the basic concept of "digital" (*era, civilization, economy, politics, personality, management, work, education, etc.*), create a new reality, a new person and a new society.

The interactive capabilities of the Internet and digital media are manifested, first of all, in the presence of opinions in the modern sense among young people, who make up the bulk of users, that is, in the opportunity to get acquainted with opinions. viewers about content and its ratings even while watching. For example, on YouTube.com you can read comments from viewers (most of whom are young) under most videos, and the number of likes under each comment reflects the importance and level of support for that opinion. among the spectators. In the comments under the video content, you can see its approval, rejection and/or criticism. In this case, the user will not be left alone with the content of the young representative, he will become the subject of communication with the opportunity to express and change his position under the influence of other people.

Often, the political activity of young people is reflected in the fact that their digital profile is multifaceted and uses several different online platforms to reach the maximum audience. Twitter, Facebook, VKontakte, Youtube, Telegram - these and other popular platforms are used among young people. They differ primarily in the type of information posted and profile maintenance. The integration of various network platforms allows different groups of voters (users) to convey their views and information in a form convenient for them. Small news, interesting thoughts, videos and photos, microblogging format are mixed in the news feed of social networks, instant messengers and are presented in proportions that young people can organize by subscribing to various profiles and groups. It is important to remember that new opportunities and technologies have emerged. For example, deep data analysis technologies, including social networks, are successfully used by the British private company Cambridge Analytica, which emerged in recent decades, to develop strategic communications. He showed his activity on the Internet during the election campaign.

From the point of view of assessing the influence of digital technologies and the media on the problem of youth political activity in literature, the space of the Internet and social networks can be considered as the space of a new civil society, the possibility of the functioning of direct democracy. The Internet and social networks, the media increase participation in elections, the number of contacts between citizens, youth and authorities increases the availability of political

information and makes it possible to use new tools for discussions between citizens and youth. Therefore, regardless of the type of media, according to supporters of this position, they not only expand, but also deepen the participation of young people in political activities, involve them in processes, since the formation of political views of a significant part of young people is, first of all, digital infrastructure (*Internet, social networks and instant messengers*) and, more generally, can contribute to community building due to their unique media capabilities that allow them to overcome geographic distance, race, and age. gender, time zones and daily routine allow. The media also have a more specific “memory effect” due to their ability to record messages. All this creates additional opportunities for the development of mutual understanding, tolerance, willingness to accept other humanitarian views and norms of behavior, and the development of common values among young people.

It's not for nothing that they say that knowledge acquired in youth is a model carved in stone. What he studied and strived for since childhood, following the requirements and advice of his parents and teachers, will definitely bear fruit in the future. Today, the path of science, which seems difficult and difficult to many people, becomes attractive and attractive when they achieve success and achieve high goals. The main reason for this is a love of books from a young age and a desire to learn science. Therefore, if it is permissible, among these studies we can recommend that young people study the culture of using the media, the culture of participation in them and, of course, positive concepts that serve to strengthen political activity. After all, young people who never stop learning and exploring can achieve a happy future in only one way - knowledge and enlightenment, the rest is useless. Every source of useful information and knowledge that serves to ensure the political activity of youth in the media also serves to strengthen the participation of youth in processes that serve the interests of the state.

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